

Electrometric Estimation of Tripotassium Oxohydroxotetra-Cyanomolybdate(IV) (TCM) and Tetrapotassium Dioxotetra-Cyanotungstate(IV) (TCT)

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The potentiometric estimation of tripotassium oxohydroxotetracyanomolybdate(IV) (TCM) using oxidants, viz. I_2 , $Cr_2O_7^{2-}$ and $Ce(IV)$, are described. Amperometry is also applied to the titrimetric determination of TCM and tetra-potassium dioxotetracyanotungstate (IV) (TCT) with hexacyanoferrate(III).

ONLY few methods are available in the literature for the estimation of oxocyanides of molybdenum and tungsten. We have reported that TCM can be estimated potentiometrically at room temperature with potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) in alkaline medium and with potassium permanganate in acidic medium.¹ Mikhalevich and Litvinchuk determined the purity of TCT by titrating potentiometrically with $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ or $KMnO_4$.² During the course of our studies on the standard potential (E°) for W(IV)-W(VI) oxocyanide complex ion couple, a potentiometric method was developed for determining the concentration of TCT. The potentiometric method involving the use of the above couple of the various oxidants, namely I_2 , $Cr_2O_7^{2-}$ and $Ce(IV)$ was found to give satisfactory results.³ Later on, these oxidants were employed to determine the purity of TCM.

The present communication deals with (i) potentiometric determination of TCM using oxidants I_2 , $Cr_2O_7^{2-}$ and $Ce(IV)$, and (ii) amperometric determination of TCM and TCT with hexacyanoferrate(III).

Experimental

Reagents

Tripotassium oxohydroxotetracyanomolybdate(IV) dihydrate, $K_3[MoO(OH)(CN)_4] \cdot 2H_2O$ (TCM)^{4,5,6}: The crystalline red-violet complex, $K_4[MoO(CN)_4]$, was prepared by the method of Jakob, *et al.*⁷ It was then hydrolysed with water to give the soluble compound, $K_3[MoO(OH)(CN)_4]$,⁴ which was isolated in the solid state by fractional precipitation with ethanol. It was kept over $CaCl_2$ in a vacuum desiccator. Its solution was standardised potentiometrically by titrating with potassium ferricyanide.¹

Tetrapotassium dioxotetracyanotungstate(IV) hexahydrate, $K_4[WO_2(CN)_4] \cdot 6H_2O$ (TCT): The crystalline

red-brown complex was prepared electrolytically by following the directions of Mikhalevich and Litvinchuk.² The complex was kept over $CaCl_2$ in a vacuum desiccator. Its purity was determined potentiometrically by titrating with potassium ferricyanide.²

Potassium hexacyanoferrate(III): The AnalaR grade product was recrystallized from water and air-dried. The iron content of the complex was determined iodometrically as $Fe(III)$.⁸

All other reagents used were either of AnalaR grade (B.D.H.) or Merck reagent-grade. Triply-distilled water was used for preparing the solutions and subsequent dilutions. The complex salt solutions were stored in amber-coloured bottles wrapped in black paper.

Apparatus:

A Pye Precision Vernier potentiometer (Cat. No. 7568) in conjunction with a ballistic galvanometer and lamp and scale arrangement was used for potential measurements. A saturated calomel electrode served as reference and a bright platinum electrode as indicator electrode. A side-tube from the reference electrode with porous end-plate, filled with KNO_3 (satd) agar, was used to connect the two halves of the cell.

The amperometric titrations were performed on a Fischer Elecdropode. A dropping mercury electrode having $t = 3.1$ sec. at $E_{a.e.} = 0.0V$ (vs. S.C.E. in $0.1M$ KNO_3) in conjunction with a S.C.E. was used for current measurements.

All measurements were made in a darkened room. A constant temperature of $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ was maintained by means of a Townson and Mercer thermostat. All operations were carried out under a nitrogen atmosphere. Cylinder nitrogen was used after passage through chromous chloride and alkaline pyrogallol solutions.

Results and Discussion

Potentiometric determination of TCM: Titrations with iodine:

An aliquot volume of the standard TCM solution is taken in a titration vessel fitted with a five-holed stopper. These holes accommodate the inlet and outlet tubes for nitrogen, the platinum indicator electrode, the limb of the saturated KNO_3 bridge and the nozzle of the microburette containing the iodine solution. Enough potassium hydroxide is added to give 1M KOH strength when diluted to 20 ml. The mixture is then diluted to 20 ml. and titrated with 0.1M iodine solution. After each addition of the titrant the mixture is stirred by means of a stream of nitrogen. Potentials are measured 1 min. after the addition of each portion of the titrant. The intensity of the blue colour of the solution decreases as the titration proceeds. At the equivalence point the solution becomes colourless. As the potential break at the equivalence point is not very high, the equivalence point of the titration is better read from curve obtained by plotting $\Delta E/\Delta V$ vs. V .

Only direct titrations (TCM solution in the cell) are possible. The course of the redox reaction may be represented by the scheme:

Determination with acid potassium dichromate:

An aliquot of standard potassium dichromate solution is taken in the titration vessel. Enough sulphuric acid is added to give 4M H_2SO_4 strength when diluted to 20 ml. The mixture is then diluted to 20 ml. and the titration is carried out with 0.1M TCM solution using the potentiometric titration assembly described above. The solution is decolorized owing to reduction of $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$. Any TCM added after the equivalence point is decomposed by the acid content of the reaction mixture. A potential break of 393 mV/0.1 ml. is obtained in the titration of 1.5 mM $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ in 4M H_2SO_4 with 0.1M TCM.

Experiments have shown that direct titrations of TCM with $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ are not possible in sulphuric acid, because of the reaction between TCM and H_2SO_4 .

Determination with acid cerium(IV) sulphate:

Since direct titrations are again impossible, $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ in a medium of 4M H_2SO_4 is titrated with 0.1M TCM. At the equivalence point, a jump in potential of 465 mV/0.05 ml. is observed in the titration of 6.0 mM $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ with 0.1M TCM.

The difference in the behaviour of various oxidants towards TCM is self evident. Only those oxidants with a high oxidation potential gave large inflexions at the equivalence point.

The amounts of various oxidants consumed in all the titrations correspond stoichiometrically to the

oxidation of hydroxocyanomolybdate(IV) to molybdate(VI)¹:

Amperometric determinations of TCM and TCT with potassium hexacyanoferrate(III):

The polarographic behaviours of TCM, TCT and potassium ferricyanide were studied in 0.1M KOH in the presence of 0.1M KNO_3 and 0.02% gelatin. Both the TCM and TCT are oxidised at dropping mercury electrode producing only one wave with wave potentials -0.315V and -0.295V respectively, in 0.1M KOH-O, 1M KNO_3 or 0.02% gelatin solution. A potential of -0.5V was chosen as the constant potential to be applied during the titrations as the ferricyanide ion, in the same medium, yields a diffusion current proportional to its concentration.

Amperometric titrations were carried out at this potential in the medium of KOH (0.1M) in presence of 0.1M KNO_3 and 0.02% gelatin. 10 ml. of the titre solution was taken in the cell each time, which was swept and stirred by bubbling purified nitrogen. The end-points were located graphically by plotting observed current values as a function of volume of the titrant added. Titrations were performed in both the direct and reverse manners.

In direct titrations, when complex cyanide was used as titre, it was observed that the observed current remains almost unchanged on the addition of potassium ferricyanide solution until the equivalence point is reached, after which the diffusion current due to $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ ions increases linearly with addition of the latter. In reverse titrations, on the addition of complex cyanide solution to ferricyanide solution, the diffusion current due to $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ ions decreases. This decrease in current continues until the equivalence point is reached and then the current remains constant due to the non-reducibility of the complex cyanide at d.m.e.

Both the complex cyanides react with ferricyanide in the molar ratio of 1:2 (oxocyanide : ferricyanide).

The reactions may be given as^{1,2}:

and

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